

Discussion paper: The impact of politicized and costly climate policies on trust in scientific information and policy support

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Abstract

By using survey experiments, we investigate how politicization and the financial cost of climate policies influence public trust in scientific information about climate change. Our results show that citizens' trust in science-based information on climate is not solely judged by its content itself, but also by its political context. When a climate policy is associated with a political affiliation, trust in the scientific information decreases compared to when the policy is politically neutral. This result is independent of the political party supporting the policy. Right-bloc voters are more likely to believe that scientific information overstates problems with climate change, irrespective of if the Conservative Party or the Green Party endorses the policy. Left-bloc voters are more likely to believe that scientific information overstates the problem with climate change only if the Green Party endorses the policy. However, there is no effect on policy support on political endorsement. Varying the financial cost of the policy to induce cognitive dissonance had no significant effect on trust in the scientific information; instead, as expected, higher cost substantially reduced policy support.

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1. Introduction

The conventional divide between the traditional left and right ideologies exemplifies a significant clash of interests. Competing political camps employ different narratives or framings to gain support for their policies. This inherent opposition among political rivals can lead to skepticism regarding opposing viewpoints and to political polarization. This can, in turn, affect voters' views on policies. For example, voters might be skeptical of a policy simply because it is endorsed or proposed by a political party they do not identify with. Extensive use of different narratives could also degrade the general trust in information coming from politicians. Moreover, political polarization might spill over to voters' views on scientific information. If they are skeptical of a policy proposed by a political party, they might also be skeptical of the underlying scientific information about the problem that the policy intends to address. Similarly, voters could oppose a policy due to its expected cost, which could also affect their belief in the underlying scientific information.¹ Beliefs are complex; while they sometimes seem rigid and fixed, people can alter their beliefs after receiving new information (Bénabou & Tirole, 2016; Sharot et al., 2023; Zimmerman, 2020). The literature on motivated beliefs suggests that beliefs often fulfill individuals' valuable psychological and functional needs, with examples such as social identity, political ideology, or religious faith (Bénabou & Tirole, 2016). People hold certain beliefs because they gain utility from them, which can explain their beliefs (Bénabou & Tirole, 2016). If beliefs change, the process can be seen as weighing the value of an old belief against the expected value of a new belief (Sharot et al., 2023). Bromberg-Martin and Sharot (2020) argue that beliefs are a source of value in and of themselves and that people are motivated to hold specific beliefs. For example, people generally prefer to believe they are correct rather than incorrect and can even purposely ignore information that contradicts their preferred worldview. Related to the topic of this study, Kahan (2011) found that whether a scientific expert is judged to be knowledgeable depends on how closely the expert's position aligns with the worldview of the person evaluating them.

¹ Polarization could even affect other non-political areas such as the decision on whether to move from a specific area or not, depending on the political affiliation of neighbors (McCartney et al., 2024), marriage decisions (Huber and Malhotra, 2017), and hiring decisions (Colonnelli et al., 2020).

In this paper, we investigate how the politicization and perceived cost of climate policies affect people's beliefs about scientific information on climate change and climate policy support. Previous research shows that climate change is a polarizing topic (see e.g., Kousser and Tranter 2018; Hornsey et al., 2016; Linde 2018; Carlsson et al., 2021). For example, Hornsey et al. (2016) examined the public's beliefs in climate change in 56 different countries. They found that ideology, worldview, and political affiliation were more important in explaining beliefs than factors such as education, gender, and experiences from extreme weather. Kousser and Tranter (2018) showed that polarization occurs when political leaders have divergent positions on climate change policy, while a closer agreement is reached among public opinions when leaders converge on a policy proposal. Carlsson et al. (2021) investigated how attitudes toward climate policies have evolved over the last ten years and found signs of increased political polarization both in the U.S. and in Sweden.

While disparities in policy endorsement between ideological groups are expected, the differences might stem not only from varying values and preferences but also from beliefs about climate change (McCright and Dunlap, 2011). However, while political parties can influence or shape individuals' beliefs, it could be that individuals' preexisting beliefs and preferences determine their choice of political party. Thus, political affiliation and beliefs alone do not allow us to determine whether beliefs are shaped by party influence or political affiliation reflect prior ideological commitments. Moreover, if beliefs are strong it is less likely that people are influenced by exogenous factors. To causally investigate how the politicization of a policy affects people's beliefs, we conduct a survey-based experiment. We vary information on (i) the political party endorsing a policy to tighten the EU emission trading system (ETS), and (ii) the cost for the household of the proposed policy. Our primary interest is not in policy support, although we investigate this as well, but instead in the beliefs about scientific information about climate change. The scientific information is taken from the IPCC reports. The two political affiliations used in the experiment are the Conservative Party, which is the largest party on the right in Sweden, and the Green Party. The Green Party and its supporters has a strong focus on climate change, while the Conservative Party and its supporters traditionally focus on economic growth as a key concern.

Consequently, we investigate whether the political affiliation of those who advocate a policy affects citizens' beliefs about whether the scientific information on climate change, based on the IPCC reports, is balanced or not. Ideologically motivated cognition implies that people maintain beliefs that indicate

their allegiance to the specific ideological group they are affiliated with. In our context, this means that respondents are likely to perceive scientific information about climate change differently based on the political affiliation of the policy proposer. If the proposer is from an opposing political camp, they may view climate change information as incorrect and exaggerated, leading them to oppose the policy. If the proposer shares their political affiliation, they are more likely to see the information as balanced or underestimate the severity of climate change, reinforcing their support. This is in line with the arguments by Sharot et al. (2023) that political polarization can stem from a process where different environments reward different sets of beliefs, e.g., social acceptance of holding certain beliefs about climate change can differ between different political camps. While this pattern of motivated reasoning is likely to hold in many cases, there are important exceptions. For instance, it seems less likely that individuals who support a party such as the Green Party would dismiss scientific information on climate change as exaggerated merely because it is endorsed by a political opponent, given that the core values of such parties are deeply aligned with environmental concern. The two parties, the Conservative Party and the Green Party, are different in many ways. The Conservative Party is one of the largest parties and is part of a clearly defined right bloc. The Green Party is much smaller and is not a clear member of any coalition, although they have been in government together with the Social Democratic Party. Hence, we are more agnostic about the behavior of the left bloc when the Green Party advocates a policy, compared to when the Conservative Party advocates the policy. For the right bloc, we can form clearer predictions based on ideologically motivated cognition.

In another treatment where no political party is mentioned, we vary the financial cost of the proposed policy, thereby introducing potential cognitive dissonance. According to Frantz and Mayer (2009), most people cannot easily avoid the production of CO₂ in their everyday life, and to avoid psychic tension coming from cognitive dissonance, people may adjust their beliefs to be consistent with their behavior. This might lead to beliefs that climate change is not a priority and to the development of self-concepts that are not pro-climate. Several studies have shown that the cost of a policy matters (see e.g. Dechezleprêtre et al., 2022; Hesterman et al., 2020; Carlsson et al., 2022). Hesterman et al. (2020) found that individuals with a larger consumption of meat are more likely to adopt self-deception, as the benefit of denying moral externality is greatest for these individuals. However, consumers become more realistic when the price of the climate-harmful good increases. Thus, an increase in the price makes consumption less appealing and decreases the incentives to deny the negative consequences of consumption. We therefore expect that a high cost for the climate policy will make individuals discredit

the climate information more than a low cost, as a higher cost implies a lower utility of entertaining beliefs about climate change and should increase the cognitive dissonance (Akerlof and Dickens, 1982). In other words, when the climate policy imposes personal and costly sacrifices, people may mistrust the climate change problem itself.

Given that politicization influences beliefs about climate change, we next investigate whether these changes in beliefs translate into differences in policy preferences. To do this, we use a contingent valuation scenario to assess how our treatments influence respondents' stated personal support, measured by their willingness to pay (WTP) for a climate change mitigation policy. Prior literature suggests that voters rely on cues from politicians when forming political preferences (Druckman et al., 2010). For instance, a recent survey experiment by Bürgisser et al. (2024) found that party cues can significantly increase the support for green taxes. Similarly, Rinscheid et al. (2021) found in a survey experiment that the endorsement of policies by political parties affects support, and that this effect depends on the voters' trust in these parties. Furthermore, policies can in turn affect preference and attitudes (Chen et al., 2025).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in Section 2, we present the experimental design of the two main treatments. In Section 3, we present the results, beginning with the effects of the treatments on beliefs in scientific information, followed by presentation of the results on policy support. Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. Experimental Design

The surveys were conducted between March and April 2023 among ordinary citizens over 18 years old living in Sweden. We designed five slightly different surveys: one control version and four treatment versions. In Treatments 1 and 2, we varied the political party that proposed the climate policy, while in Treatments 3 and 4, we varied the cost of the policy. The final survey yielded 2,656 responses: 703 responses for the control version, 707 responses for Treatment 1, 710 for Treatment 2, 255 for Treatment 3, and 281 for Treatment 4. The following structure applies to the control and first two treatments of the survey: The first section provided a summary of information about the IPCC and its key findings on climate change. Additionally, respondents were informed about the EU Emission Trading System (ETS) and its significance as a policy to mitigate climate change. We explained that the system is currently under revision due to concerns that it is not powerful enough and needs to be

tightened. The revision complies with the Paris Agreement, aiming to achieve near-zero emissions by 2035 in the EU, and a more stringent cap also implies higher prices for food, transportation, and energy for EU residents. After receiving the information, respondents were asked to assess the credibility of the IPCC information on a scale between 1 and 10. The full question is presented in Figure 1.

“How would you summarize the information you previously received from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) about global climate change and its environmental impact? If you want to read the information again, click here [Climate Change Information]. Answer on a scale of 1 to 10, where 1 is that the information grossly overestimates climate change and its impact on the environment, 5 is that the information about climate change and its impact on the environment is balanced and credible, and 10 that the information underestimates climate change and its impact on the environment.”

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
The information grossly overestimates climate change and its impact on the environment.				Information on climate change and its impact on the environment is balanced and credible.					The information underestimates climate change and its impact on the environment.

Figure 1. Question about belief in scientific information about climate change and its impact on the environment

In the next section, we asked the respondent for their willingness to pay (WTP) for tightening the EU ETS system. In the final section of the survey, participants provided their socio-economic details.

As mentioned, we had five slightly different surveys: one control version and four treatment versions. In treatment 1, the respondents were informed that the Conservative Party (the largest right-wing party in Sweden, currently leading the government) supports the suggestion to tighten emissions trading in the EU ETS system. In treatment 2, respondents were told that the Green Party supports the suggestions to tighten the same trading system. In reality, none of the parties in the Swedish parliament have opposed tightening the EU ETS system (Naturskyddsföreningen, 2022). In the control treatment version of the survey, we did not link the policy suggestion to any political party. Instead, we wrote that the EU ETS system was currently under review, and there was a general concern that the system was not powerful enough and needed to be tightened. This is also true for treatments 3 and 4. The only difference between treatments 3 and 4 is the hypothetical framing of the annual cost of a more stringent ETS cap. In Treatment 3, respondents were asked to consider a scenario where the cost was framed as

low, corresponding to 250 SEK per household annually. In Treatment 4, the cost was framed as high, corresponding to 5,000 SEK per household annually. In both cases, respondents were asked whether their household would be willing to pay the specified amount for a tightening of the emissions trading system.² Compared to the control and Treatments 1 and 2, the structure of the survey is slightly different for Treatments 3 and 4. Specifically, for Treatments 3 and 4, the WTP question comes before subjects are asked to assess the credibility of the IPCC information. This allows us to test for a possible cognitive dissonance in how scientific information is perceived after a low or high cost, respectively. Another difference is that Treatments 3 and 4 used a closed-ended payment question, where respondents accept or reject a fixed bid (250 and 5000 SEK), while the other versions used the payment card method, allowing respondents to choose their maximum WTP from a range of amounts.

3. Results

3.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 1 presents the distributions of the covariates in the treatment and control groups. The random assignment created experimental groups with only minor differences regarding age and income. However, treatment 4 has a slightly lower share of university-educated respondents compared to all other groups (35% compared to 38%). These small variations are consistent with what can be expected by chance, indicating that the randomization process was successful.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics – the balance between treatments

	Control		T1		T2		T3 – low cost		T4 – high cost	
	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd
Male	0.50		0.50		0.51		0.51		0.50	
Age	50.13	18.43	50.66	18.59	51.09	17.97	50.11	19.02	50.20	18.68
University	0.38		0.38		0.38		0.38		0.35	
Househ. size	2.33	1.19	2.34	1.66	2.34	1.45	2.39	1.26	2.54	1.91

² More specifically, the respondents were given the following information in treatment 4 “A tightening of the EU Emissions Trading System involves a substantial one-time reduction in the total number of emission allowances within the EU, as well as a larger annual decrease in the number of allowances than previously stated. This tightening also means increased costs for all households in the EU each year until 2035. The cost will primarily be borne through higher fuel and energy prices. Imagine that you and all other households will have to pay a significant annual cost of 5,000 SEK until 2035. This cost will be adjusted for inflation over time. The increased cost will impact your ability to purchase other goods or allocate resources to other initiatives. Would your household be willing to pay this amount annually to tighten the emissions trading system?”

Income	40700	25154	38034	25384	39634	25119	39657	26426	40302	25641
Right-bloc	0.43		0.42		0.39		0.37		0.41	
Left-bloc	0.30		0.33		0.34		0.38		0.33	
Green Party	0.04		0.03		0.04		0.03		0.02	
Center Party	0.04		0.03		0.03		0.02		0.05	
Other party	0.19		0.19		0.21		0.20		0.19	
Obs.	703		707		710		255		281	

We group respondents into a Right-leaning and a Left-leaning bloc based on their answers to a question about which political party they believe best aligns with their views. The Conservative Party is currently, as well as at the time the experiment was conducted, the leading party in the Right-bloc Government. The Right-bloc Government also includes two other Right-leaning parties (the Liberal Party and the Christian Democrats). In addition, the Swedish Democrats, a Right-Wing populist party, co-operates closely with the Government and acts as a support party for them. The Left bloc consists of the biggest party in Sweden, the Social Democrats, and the Left Party, which is more to the left in their politics compared to the Social Democrats. This is the traditional division in Sweden. However, before the current government, the Social Democrats formed a government together with the Green Party (2018-2022). This government was supported by the Left Party, the Liberal Party, and the Center Party. In the survey, we asked about where on the left-right scale respondents would place themselves on a scale between 1 and 10. We also asked how concerned they are with climate change (on a scale between 1 and 5). In the figure below, we plot the average scores for these two questions for supporters of the nine political parties.

Figure 1. Mean values responses to questions about where on the left-right scale respondents would put themselves and their concern about climate change, for supporters of each political party.

We can see that there is a strong similarity in expressed preferences within the two political blocs. The major exception is supporters of the Liberal Party in the Right bloc. Also in the left bloc, the Left Party supporters are more left-leaning than the supporters of the Social Democratic Party. Moreover, the Green Party has, as expected, supporters who are the most concerned with climate change, but there are no large differences from supporters of the left bloc. The Green Party supporters are also between the two left bloc parties on the left-right scale. Thus, while the Conservative Party is a clear ideological opponent to the left bloc, it is less obvious when it comes to the Green Party. It is clearer that the Green Party is an ideological opponent of the right bloc. Moreover, there is in general a stronger concern about climate change among the left bloc and the Green Party supporters.

In Table 2, we report the distribution of political attitudes among the whole sample. Table 2 also shows that the distribution of political preferences in our sample corresponds well with political party preferences conducted by Statistics Sweden (2023), with one exception. The share of those who vote for the Social Democratic Party is significantly lower in our sample. Importantly, the shares for those two parties we use as the senders of scientific information (the Conservative Party and the Green Party), are in line with the actual numbers at the time of the survey. In the econometric analysis, we will use survey weights for each of the political parties, using the observed shares in the political party preference survey as population shares.

Table 2. Distribution of political attitudes among the whole sample and according to the political party preference survey at the time of the survey (Statistics of Sweden, 2023)

	Sample	Political Party Preference Survey, May 2023 (Statistics of Sweden)
Right bloc (current government)	41%	36%
Conservative Party	17%	16%
Liberal Party	3%	3%
Christian Democrats	4%	3%
Sweden Democrats	17%	14%
Left bloc	33%	37%
Social Democrats	25%	30%
Left Party	8%	7%
Center Party	3%	• 4%
Green Party	3%	• 4%
Other (do not know, other parties, refuse)	20%	• 21%

Swedish citizens have, in general, a high confidence in research. In a recent survey, 86 percent expressed a high level of trust on a four-point scale. However, the trust varies with political views: 81

percent of the right bloc expresses a high level of trust, while 93 percent among the supporters of the left bloc express a high level of trust (Vetenskap & Allmänhet, 2024).

3.2 Effects on belief about scientific information from the IPCC

We will now explore people’s beliefs about the climate change information from the IPCC provided in the survey. Responses are grouped into three groups: (i) The scientific information about climate change is *balanced* (rating of 5), ii) the scientific information *underestimates* climate change (ratings between 1-4), and iii) the scientific information *overestimates* climate change (ratings between 6 and 10). The full distribution of responses is presented in Table A1 in the appendix.

Figure 2 shows that, in general, people believe the information provided is balanced. However, there are notable differences between the treatments. The share of respondents who state that the information is balanced and credible is 62 percent in the control group, 55 percent in the Conservative party treatment, and 50 percent in the Green party treatment. The shares of those who believe the information underestimated the climate change problem are stable (around 20%) across the three versions of the survey. However, if the climate policy is proposed by either the Conservative Party or the Green Party, more subjects believe the information overestimates climate change and its impact on the environment, despite these two political parties having generally different approaches to climate change and how it should be handled.

Figure 2: How subjects perceive information on climate change, control, and treatments with political endorsement.

We will now turn to the control group to explore political polarization in the perception of scientific information about climate change. We estimate a multinomial logit model with three categories: (i) the information underestimates climate change and its impact on the environment (ratings between 1-4), (ii) the information is balanced (rating of 5), and (iii) the information overestimates climate change and its impact on the environment (ratings between 6-10). We include a set of socio-economic

characteristics and a dummy variable for the Right-bloc and for those voting for other parties, with the Left-bloc as the reference category. Results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Multinomial logit model on the perception of scientific information, only the control group; marginal effects.

	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Male	-0.136*** (0.036)	0.038 (0.030)	0.098*** (0.028)
University	-0.010 (0.037)	0.036 (0.030)	-0.026 (0.030)
Age	0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)
Right Bloc	-0.078 (0.041)	-0.062 (0.033)	0.140*** (0.032)
Other	-0.043 (0.051)	-0.025 (0.039)	0.069 (0.044)
<i>N</i>	703		

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05

There indeed is a statistically significant political polarization in beliefs about information on climate change. People on the right side of the political spectrum are more likely to believe that the information overestimates climate change compared to those on the left. The difference is sizeable: the likelihood increases by 14 percentage points if a person identifies with the Right Bloc compared to the Left Bloc. Additionally, males are more likely to hold this opinion than females.

Next, to causally investigate how the politicization of a policy affects people’s beliefs, we turn our focus to potential differences between the control and treatment versions. We again estimate a multinomial logit model with the same three categories, and we include two dummy variables for the two treatments. This is to detect any treatment differences. Results of the whole sample are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. The political identity of policy proposer: marginal effects from Multinomial logit model on beliefs considering scientific information about climate change from the IPCC. Whole sample.

	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-0.064* (0.027)	0.008 (0.022)	0.056* (0.023)
Treatment 2 (Green Party)	-0.119*** (0.026)	0.026 (0.021)	0.092*** (0.022)
<i>N</i>	2,119		

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05

If the climate policy is proposed by any of the political parties, it is more likely that people believe the scientific information is biased compared to the control version. For example, if the information comes

from the Conservative Party, the likelihood of perceiving that the information from the IPCC is overestimating climate change increases by 6 percentage points compared to the control group. If instead the climate policy is proposed by the Green Party, the likelihood of perceiving that the information overestimates climate change increases by about 10 percentage points.³ In summary, we find that politicization of the policy has a negative spill-over effect on scientific information and makes it appear less balanced than otherwise.

As we have discussed, the political views of the respondents may affect the extent to which the political identity of the messenger affects the beliefs about climate change. Moreover, we know that there is a difference in the view of scientific information between those who identify with the Right Bloc compared to those who identify with the Left Bloc, even in the control group. Hence, we next assess the heterogeneity in the average treatment depending on the subjects' political affiliation. We therefore estimate separate models for respondents supporting the Right- and Left-Bloc, using the control and treatment groups. Results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Marginal effects from Multinomial logit model on beliefs considering scientific information about climate change from the IPCC, separate models for Right- and Left-Blocs.

	Right-Bloc		
	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-0.079* (0.040)	0.001 (0.028)	0.078* (0.039)
Treatment 2 (Green Party)	-0.088* (0.041)	-0.027 (0.030)	0.115** (0.039)
<i>N</i>	879		
	Left-Bloc		
	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-0.053 (0.047)	0.005 (0.042)	0.048 (0.037)
Treatment 2 (Green Party)	-0.139** (0.045)	0.053 (0.040)	0.086* (0.035)
<i>N</i>	683		

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05

³ The results are robust to controlling for respondent's socio-economic characteristics (age, university education, and gender) and political attitudes; results available upon request from the authors.

Right-bloc voters are more likely to think that scientific information overestimates climate change in the two treatment groups compared with the control group, irrespective of what political party supports the proposed climate policy. Thus, for these voters, it is the mere politicization of the policy that results in an effect on their beliefs. Among Left Bloc voters, the pattern is different. If the policy is supported by the Conservative Party, there is no difference in beliefs compared with the control group. Based on ideologically motivated cognition, one would expect that they would find the scientific information to overestimate climate change if the Conservative Party supports the policy. One explanation for not finding this could be that, in general, there is a stronger concern with climate change among these voters, in particular compared with supporters and representatives of the Conservative Party. When the policy is supported by the Green Party, individuals are more likely to believe that scientific information overestimates the severity of climate change. This is consistent with the expectations of ideologically motivated cognition if voters view the Green Party as an ideological opponent to the left bloc. On the other hand, as mentioned before, we are rather agnostic about the behavior of the left bloc when the Green Party advocates a policy as the Green Party is not a clear member of any coalition but have in the past been in government together with the Social Democratic Party.

These findings offer little to no support for the theory of ideologically motivated cognition in our setting, which suggests that individuals form beliefs that reflect their ideological affiliations (Kahan, 2013). In the Appendix (Tables A2 and A3), we show the results of those who vote for the Conservative Party and the Green Party, i.e., for the two political parties we, in our experiment, claim to have proposed the stricter climate policy. The sample sizes are too small to find statistically significant results, but the beliefs of the Green Party voters are well in line with the results of the Left-Wing voters, as shown in Table 5. But when it comes to the Conservative Party voters, they experience scientific information as more balanced compared to all the Right-Wing voters when the policy proposer is the Conservative Party.⁴

⁴ In addition to the Right-bloc where the Swedish Democrats party (the support party for the Government) is included, we also estimated Table 5 only for those who vote for the three Right-Wing parties included in the Government. The results are shown in the Appendix (Table A4). The signs of the results tell the same story, i.e., that respondents experience the scientific information as excessive, but the marginal effects are not statistically significant.

Next, we examine the experimental variation in the cost of climate policy for individual households. This approach aims to evoke different levels of cognitive dissonance and assess whether this impacts the level of trust in scientific information. Figure 3 presents the distributions of responses, while Table 6 shows the marginal effects from a multinomial logit model.

Figure 3: How subjects perceive information on climate change, high- and low-cost treatments.

Table 6: Cost of climate policy: marginal Effects Multinomial logit model on belief about scientific information about climate change from the IPCC.

	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 4 (High cost)	-0.016 (0.043)	0.019 (0.034)	-0.002 (0.038)
<i>N</i>	536		

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05

Despite the huge difference in the cost to the households (250 vs. 5000 annual SEK per household) between treatments 3 and 4, we see no statistically significant effect on the beliefs about scientific climate change information. Most respondents believe that the scientific information is balanced in both cost treatments.⁵ Accordingly, we find no indication that higher financial costs trigger cognitive dissonance affecting trust in scientific information.

3.2 Effects on policy support

Given that politicization affects beliefs about climate change, we next examine whether these belief changes translate into differences in policy preferences. For the control group and Treatments 1 and 2, support for the policy is measured in terms of their stated willingness to pay (WTP) for the EU ETS system, elicited using a payment card method. The payment was annual and until the year 2035. We estimate interval regression models, with right-censoring for those who stated a WTP outside the range of the payment card. For treatments 3 and 4, policy support is measured in terms of a yes or no response to the low or high cost of the policy. In this case, we estimate policy support using a linear probability model (OLS), where the dependent variable is equal to one if the policy is supported. The independent variables include a treatment dummy and controls for political preferences.⁶ Results are presented in Table 7.

⁵ The results are robust to controlling for respondent’s socio-economic characteristics and political attitudes; results available upon request from the authors.

⁶ We find similar marginal effects using a probit model.

Table 7: Regression models policy support expressed as willingness to pay.

	(1) WTP all (Interval reg.)	(2) WTP Right Bloc (Interval reg.)	(3) WTP Left Bloc (OLS)	(4) WTP High/low cost (OLS)
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-17.88 (32.25)	-3.23 (44.35)	-25.20 (59.91)	
Treatment 2 (Green Party)	-69.04* (32.22)	-72.13 (45.10)	3.16 (59.41)	
Right bloc	-286.82*** (29.54)			-0.29*** (0.04)
Party Unknown	-256.33*** (36.41)			-0.29*** (0.06)
Treatment 4 (High cost)				-0.23*** (0.04)
Constant	650.15*** (28.83)	357.88*** (31.34)	631.72*** (42.83)	0.75*** (0.04)
Observations	1,988	852	734	532
R-squared				0.139

Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01, * p<0.05

In model 1, (WTP for all), we see that policy support depends on the political preferences of the respondents and that it also depends on the treatment. Right-bloc supporters have, on average, a markedly lower WTP than Left-bloc supporters. In addition, WTP is lower in the treatment where the Green Party supports the policy compared to the control group. If we estimate separate models for the right- and left-bloc voters (models 2 and 3), we see that the effect of Treatment 2 is largely driven by right-bloc voters. However, the effect is not statistically significant.⁷

As expected, the policy support is highly dependent on the cost of the policy, with considerably lower support if the cost is high. Thus, while we do not find that a high cost has a significant impact on the trustworthiness of the scientific information, a high cost does significantly decrease the willingness to support the EU ETS system policy (model 4). The probability of saying yes to the policy decreases by 23 percentage points if the treatment cost is 5,000 SEK instead of 250 SEK.

⁷ We also estimate separate regression models for Moderate Party and the Green Party voters. Here sample sizes are even smaller, and none of the treatment effects are statistically significant (Table A5).

4. Conclusions and Discussion

In this study, we investigated whether citizens' beliefs about science-based climate information from the IPCC are solely influenced by the content of that information or if they consider additional factors, such as the political affiliation of those proposing a climate policy. The experimental manipulation involved either including or excluding the political affiliation of those who proposed a policy related to the scientific findings. We conducted a survey experiment with five slightly different versions: one control version and four treatment versions. In Treatment 1, respondents were informed that the Conservative Party supports the suggestion to tighten the EU's emissions trading system (EU ETS). In Treatment 2, respondents were informed that the Green Party supports the suggestions to tighten the EU ETS. In the control version of the survey, we did not associate the policy suggestion with any political party. Instead, we stated that the EU ETS was under review and there was a general concern that the system was not robust enough and needed to be strengthened.

Moreover, people are compelled to initiate motivated reasoning to lessen the amount of cognitive dissonance they feel. We therefore included another treatment where we varied the financial cost of climate policy to manipulate the feeling of cognitive dissonance and investigate if that, in turn, affects the level of trust placed in the scientific information. We hypothesized that a high personal cost for the climate policy would make individuals discredit the climate information more than a low cost. In Treatment 3, respondents were told that a more stringent ETS cap would have a low annual cost corresponding to 250 SEK/household, while in Treatment 4, it was framed as a high annual cost of 5000 SEK/household.

In line with the results by Carlsson et. al. (2021), we find a clear political polarization between right-wing and left-wing voters in Sweden. Right-wing voters are more likely to believe that scientific information overestimates the problem with climate change, also in the control treatment. In addition, the likelihood of believing that scientific information overestimates the problem is even higher among the right-bloc voters if they were told that a political party, regardless of which, proposed the policy. Thus, for these voters, it is the mere politicization of the issues that strengthens their beliefs. Left-bloc voters respond partly differently; they do not react if the policy is supported by the Conservative Party, while they are more likely to believe that the scientific problem overstates the problem if the policy is supported by the Green Party. Thus, within the context of our study, we find little to no support for the theory of ideologically motivated cognition. Note, however, that we still find significant political

polarization in beliefs about climate change information (based on the analysis of our control group). Right-leaning individuals are 14 percentage points more likely than those on the left to believe the information overstates climate change. As we find limited evidence that these results are driven by ideologically motivated cognition, while we still see political polarization in beliefs about climate change information, our results suggest that individuals' preexisting beliefs and preferences affect their political preferences, their choice of political party rather than beliefs becoming polarized along party lines.

Using the financial cost of climate policy to manipulate feelings of cognitive dissonance did not influence citizens' trust in scientific information, but a higher cost significantly decreases the likelihood of paying for the climate policy itself. Thus, we conclude that we do have political polarization when it comes to both scientific information about climate change and the EU ETS policy to handle it. We also conclude that the politicization of the policy has a stronger impact on the trust in scientific information from the IPCC than the cost of the policy.

In summary, our results show that when a climate policy is based on scientific information and aligned with any political affiliation, trust in the scientific information is significantly lower compared to information without any political affiliation. While there is broad consensus on the value of evidence-based policy, our findings complicate this narrative by revealing potential negative spillover effects on trust in scientific information. Thus, although climate policies are shaped by politics, our results underscore the complex interplay between science and normative commitments in addressing societal challenges. We believe that climate policy is and should be a political issue, but it is important to be aware of that this might affect trust in science. Without greater convergence on policy proposals across party lines and stronger collaboration on major issues such as climate change, public trust in climate-related scientific information is unlikely to increase.

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Appendix:

Table A1 Distributions of the shares of respondents who believe that the scientific information is balanced, underestimated, or overestimated.

	Control	T1	T2
Balanced	62%	55%	50%
Underestimates	19%	20%	21%
Overestimates	19%	25%	29%
N	703	707	710

Table A2. Marginal effects from Multinomial logit model on beliefs considering scientific information about climate change from the IPCC, of those voting for the Conservative Party.

	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	0.007 (0.066)	-0.025 (0.047)	0.017 (0.061)
Treatment 2 (Green Party)	-0.042 (0.066)	-0.033 (0.048)	0.075 (0.059)
N	344	344	344

Table A3. Marginal effects from Multinomial logit model on beliefs considering scientific information about climate change from the IPCC, of those voting for the Green Party.

	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-0.029 (0.142)	-0.010 (0.139)	0.038 (0.069)
Treatment 2 (Green Party)	-0.064 (0.139)	0.116 (0.130)	-0.052 (0.091)
N	76	76	76

Table A4. Marginal effects from Multinomial logit model on beliefs considering scientific information about climate change from the IPCC, of those voting for one of the three parties included in the Government where the Conservative party is the largest party

	Balanced	Underestimates	Overestimates
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-0.034 (0.053)	-0.030 (0.038)	0.063 (0.048)
Treatment 2 (The Green Party)	-0.042 (0.055)	-0.049 (0.040)	0.091 (0.048)
N	502	502	502

Table A5. WTP for those who vote for the Conservative Party and for those who vote for the Green Party. Standard deviations in parentheses.

	WTP (Conservative party voter)	WTP (Green Party voters)
Treatment 1 (Conservative Party)	-60.44 (83.84)	-14.87 (233.23)
Treatment 2 (The Green Party)	-45.86 (85.05)	446.35 (161.58)
N	344	76